

ON THE EIGENSTRUCTURES OF BICOMPLEX K-POTENT MATRICES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we have studied Bicomplex k -Potent matrices satisfies the equation $A^k = \alpha I + \beta A$, where $A \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$, k is a positive integer, α and β are real numbers. This class of Bicomplex matrices includes Idempotent, Involutory, Nilpotent, Periodic, Skew-periodic, Generalized Involutory, Generalized Skew-Involutory and many more. We have investigated the Eigenstructure of Bicomplex k -Potent matrices and their diagonalizability.

Keywords: Bicomplex Matrix, Idempotent Matrix, Nilpotent Matrix, Involutory Matrix, Periodic Matrix, Skew-Periodic Matrix, Unipotent Matrix, Eigenvalue, Diagonalizable Matrix.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Yan Wu and Daniel F. Linder [10] studied a class of k -potent complex matrix

$$\{A \in \mathbb{C}_1^{n \times n} : A^k = \alpha I + \beta A, \alpha\beta = 0, \alpha, \beta \in \{-1, 0, 1\}, k \geq 2\}.$$

They called Unipotent matrix which satisfies $A^k = I$, k is a index of A and Skew-unipotent matrix which satisfies $A^k = -I$, k is index of A but the structure of these matrix differ from Unipotent matrix so we renamed such matrix as Generalized involutory and Generalized Skew-involutory matrix. In that sense $A \in \mathbb{C}_1^{n \times n}$ is said to be Generalized Involutory Matrix of index k if $A^k = I$, where k is the least positive integer and Generalized Skew-Involutory matrix of index k if $A^k = -I$, where k is the least positive integer. They show that Periodic, Skew-periodic, Generalized Involutory and Generalized Skew-Involutory Matrices are diagonalizable.

II. Bicomplex Matrix ([1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9])

We denote $\mathbb{C}_2^{m \times n} = \{A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} : \xi_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}_2\}$ the set of $m \times n$ matrices with bicomplex entries.

Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{m \times n} \Rightarrow \xi_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}_2$

2.1 Idempotent Representation of Bicomplex Matrix

(I) $\mathbb{C}^{m \times n}(i_1)$ -idempotent representation of Bicomplex Matrix

Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{m \times n}$

$$A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} = [{}^1\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} e_1 + [{}^2\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} e_2 = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2, \text{ where } {}^1A = [{}^1\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n}, {}^2A = [{}^2\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}(i_1)$$

(II) $\mathbb{C}^{m \times n}(i_2)$ -idempotent representation Bicomplex Matrix

Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{m \times n}$

$$A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} = [{}^1\xi_{1,ij}]_{m \times n} e_1 + [{}^2\xi_{2,ij}]_{m \times n} e_2 = A_1 e_1 + A_2 e_2, \text{ where } A_1 = [{}^1\xi_{1,ij}]_{m \times n}, A_2 = [{}^2\xi_{2,ij}]_{m \times n} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}(i_2)$$

2.2. Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors of a Bicomplex Matrix

2.2.1 Eigenvalues of a Bicomplex Matrix

Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ and $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}_2$, then the matrix $A - \lambda I$ is called the characteristic matrix of A and $P(\lambda) = \det(A - \lambda I)$ is called characteristic polynomial of A .

The equation $\det(A - \lambda I) = 0$ is called the characteristic equation of A and the roots of this equation are called characteristic roots or latent roots or characteristic values or eigenvalues of the matrix A . The set of all eigenvalues of the matrix A is denoted by $A(\lambda)$.

Note 2.1: $A(\lambda) = {}^1A({}^1\lambda)e_1 + {}^2A({}^2\lambda)e_2$ is the collection of all eigenvalues of A iff ${}^1A({}^1\lambda)$ and ${}^2A({}^2\lambda)$ are spectrum of 1A and 2A respectively.

2.2.2 Eigenvectors of a Bicomplex Matrix

Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ and $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}_2$ is an eigenvalue of A , then there exist $X = {}^1X e_1 + {}^2X e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times 1}$, ${}^1X \neq 0$ and ${}^2X \neq 0$ such that $AX = \lambda X$, then X is called characteristic vector or eigenvector of A corresponding to the eigenvalue λ .

Theorem 2.1: Let $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$, ${}^1A, {}^2A \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}(i_1)$. Then A is diagonalizable iff 1A and 2A are diagonalizable.

Bicomplex Nilpotent Matrix 2.1:

The bicomplex square matrix $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be a bicomplex nilpotent matrix of index $k_1 e_1 + k_2 e_2$ if 1A and 2A are the nilpotent matrices of indices k_1 and k_2 , respectively.

In particular $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be bicomplex nilpotent matrix of index k if 1A and 2A are the nilpotent matrices of index k .

Bicomplex Unipotent Matrix 2.2:

The bicomplex square matrix $U \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be bicomplex unipotent matrix if $U = I + N$, where I is the identity matrix and N is nilpotent.

Bicomplex Periodic Matrix 2.3:

The bicomplex square matrix $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be a bicomplex periodic matrix of period $k_1 e_1 + k_2 e_2$ if 1A and 2A are the periodic matrix of periods k_1 and k_2 , respectively.

In particular $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be a bicomplex periodic matrix of period k if 1A and 2A are the periodic matrices of period k .

Bicomplex Skew-Periodic Matrix 2.4:

The bicomplex square matrix $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be bicomplex skew-periodic matrix of period $k_1 e_1 + k_2 e_2$ if 1A and 2A are the skew-periodic matrix of periods k_1 and k_2 , respectively.

In particular $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be a bicomplex skew-periodic matrix of period k if 1A and 2A are the skew-periodic matrices of period k .

Generalized Bicomplex Involutionary Matrix 2.5:

The bicomplex square matrix $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be generalized bicomplex involutionary matrix of index $k_1 e_1 + k_2 e_2$ if 1A and 2A are the generalized involutionary matrix of indices k_1 and k_2 , respectively.

In particular $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be a generalized bicomplex involutionary matrix of index k if 1A and 2A are the generalized involutionary matrix of index k .

Example 2.1:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ ae_1 & 0 & 0 \\ be_1 + de_2 & ce_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow {}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a & 0 & 0 \\ b & c & 0 \end{bmatrix}, {}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ d & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$${}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a & 0 & 0 \\ b & c & 0 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^1A)^2 \neq 0, ({}^1A)^3 = 0 \Rightarrow {}^1A \text{ is a nilpotent matrix of index } 3$$

$${}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ d & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^2A)^2 = 0 \Rightarrow {}^2A \text{ is a nilpotent matrix of index } 2$$

Therefore $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is a nilpotent matrix of index $3e_1 + 2e_2$.

Example 2.2:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} e_2 & e_1 - e_2 \\ e_2 & -e_2 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow {}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, {}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$${}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^1A)^2 = 0 \Rightarrow {}^1A \text{ is a nilpotent matrix of index } 2.$$

$${}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^2A)^2 = 0 \Rightarrow {}^2A \text{ is a nilpotent matrix of index } 2.$$

Therefore $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is a nilpotent matrix of index 2.

Example 2.3:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} e_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e_2 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow A^2 = \begin{bmatrix} e_1^2 & 0 \\ 0 & e_2^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e_2 \end{bmatrix} = A$$

$\Rightarrow A$ is idempotent matrix.

Example 2.4:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 e_1 & e_2 \\ -e_2 & -i_1 e_1 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow {}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -i_1 \end{bmatrix}, {}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$${}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -i_1 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^1A)^4 = I \Rightarrow {}^1A \text{ is a periodic matrix with period 4}$$

$${}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^2A)^2 = -I \Rightarrow ({}^2A)^4 = I \Rightarrow {}^2A \text{ is a periodic matrix with period 4}$$

Therefore $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is a periodic matrix with period 4.

Example 2.5:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 e_1 & i_1 e_2 \\ -i_1 e_2 & -i_1 e_1 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow {}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -i_1 \end{bmatrix}, {}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & i_1 \\ -i_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$${}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -i_1 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^1A)^4 = I \Rightarrow {}^1A \text{ is a periodic matrix with period 4}$$

$${}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & i_1 \\ -i_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^2A)^2 = I \Rightarrow {}^2A \text{ is a periodic matrix with period 2}$$

Therefore $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is a periodic matrix with period $4e_1 + 2e_2$.

III. Class of Bicomplex k – potent Matrices

The class of Bicomplex k – potent Matrix defined as

$$T = \left\{ A = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n} : A^k = \alpha I + \beta A, \alpha\beta = 0, \alpha, \beta \in \{-1, 0, 1\}, k \geq 2 \right\}$$

We consider those Bicomplex matrices in the class T that satisfy the following condition

If $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is a bicomplex k – potent Matrix, then both 1A and 2A are k – potent Matrix i.e. k is the smallest positive integer for which $({}^1A)^k = \alpha I + \beta {}^1A$ and $({}^2A)^k = \alpha I + \beta {}^2A$.

Precisely, If k is the index of $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$, so k is the index of both 1A and 2A .

Case(i) For $k = 2, \alpha = 0, \beta = 1, A^2 = A$ i.e. A is a Bicomplex idempotent matrix

Case(ii) For $\alpha = 0, \beta = 1, A^k = A$ i.e. A is a Bicomplex periodic matrix. If k is the index of A , then A is the Bicomplex periodic matrix with period $k - 1$.

Case(iii) For $\alpha = 0, \beta = -1, A^k = -A$ i.e. A is Bicomplex Skew-periodic matrix. If k is the index of A , then A is the Bicomplex Skew-periodic matrix with period $k - 1$.

Case(iv) For $k = k, \alpha = 0, \beta = 0, A^k = O$. If k is the index of A , then A is the Bicomplex Nilpotent Matrix of index k .

Case(v) For $k = 2, \alpha = 1, \beta = 0, A^2 = I$ i.e. A is Bicomplex involutory matrix.

Case(vi) For $k = k, \alpha = 1, \beta = 0, A^k = I$. If k is the index of A , then A is the Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrix of index k .

Case(vii) For $k = k, \alpha = -1, \beta = 0, A^k = -I$. If k is the index of A , then A is the Generalized Bicomplex Skew-involutory matrix of index k .

Proposition 3.1:

Let $N \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a nilpotent matrix of index m and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then $\lambda = 0$.

Proof: Let $N \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a nilpotent matrix of index m

Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix N associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\Rightarrow NX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow N(NX) = N(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow N^2X = \lambda(NX)$$

$$\Rightarrow N^2X = \lambda(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow N^2X = \lambda^2 X$$

$$\Rightarrow N^m X = \lambda^m X$$

$$\Rightarrow OX = \lambda^m X \quad (\because N^m = O)$$

$$\Rightarrow O = \lambda^m X$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda^m X = O$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda^m {}^1X e_1 + {}^2\lambda^m {}^2X e_2 = O$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda^m {}^1X = 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda^m {}^2X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda^m = 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda^m = 0 \quad (\because {}^1X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2X \neq 0)$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda = 0$$

Proposition 3.2:

Let $N \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a non-zero nilpotent matrix of index m , then N is not diagonalizable.

Proof: Let N is diagonalizable

\Rightarrow There exist an invertible matrix $P \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$

such that $P^{-1}NP = D$

According to proposition 3.1, eigenvalues of N are zero

$$\Rightarrow D = O$$

$\Rightarrow N = O$, contradicting that N is non-zero matrix.

Proposition 3.3:

Let $U \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a Unipotent Matrix of index m and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then $\lambda = 1$.

Proof: $U = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a unipotent matrix of index m

$\Rightarrow U = I + N$, where I is the identity matrix and N is nilpotent of index m

Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix U associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\Rightarrow UX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow (I + N)X = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow X + NX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow NX = (\lambda - 1)X$$

$$\Rightarrow N(NX) = (\lambda - 1)NX$$

$$\Rightarrow N^2X = (\lambda - 1)^2X \quad (\because NX = (\lambda - 1)X)$$

$$\Rightarrow N^m X = (\lambda - 1)^m X$$

$$\Rightarrow OX = (\lambda - 1)^m X \quad (\because N^m = O)$$

$$\Rightarrow O = (\lambda - 1)^m X$$

$$\Rightarrow (\lambda - 1)^m X = O$$

$$\Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda - 1)({}^1X) e_1 + ({}^2\lambda - 1)({}^2X) e_2 = O$$

$$\Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda - 1)^m = 0 \text{ and } ({}^2\lambda - 1)^m = 0 \quad (\because {}^1X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2X \neq 0)$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 1$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda = 1$$

Proposition 3.4: Let $A \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a periodic matrix of period k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

$$\lambda \in \{0\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2p\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 \mid p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2q\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \\ \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2p\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 + e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2q\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

Proof: Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix A associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\Rightarrow AX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow A(AX) = A(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda(AX)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda^2 X$$

$$\Rightarrow A^{k+1} X = \lambda^{k+1} X$$

$$\Rightarrow AX = \lambda^{k+1} X \quad (\because A^{k+1} = A)$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda X = \lambda^{k+1} X$$

$$\Rightarrow (\lambda - \lambda^{k+1}) X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda - {}^1\lambda^{k+1}) {}^1 X e_1 + ({}^2\lambda - {}^2\lambda^{k+1}) {}^2 X e_2 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda - {}^1\lambda^{k+1}) {}^1 X = 0 \text{ and } ({}^2\lambda - {}^2\lambda^{k+1}) {}^2 X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda - {}^1\lambda^{k+1} = 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda - {}^2\lambda^{k+1} = 0 \quad (\because {}^1 X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2 X \neq 0)$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda(1 - {}^1\lambda^k) = 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda(1 - {}^2\lambda^k) = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 0, (1)^\frac{1}{k} \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 0, (1)^\frac{1}{k}$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 0, e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2p\pi}{k} \right)}; p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 0, e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2q\pi}{k} \right)}; q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda \in \{0\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2p\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 \mid p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2q\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \\ \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2p\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 + e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2q\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

Note 3.1: Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a periodic matrix of period k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

(i) A contains $(k+1)^2$ distinct eigenvalues

(ii) $\|\lambda\| \in \left\{ 0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1 \right\}$

Proposition 3.5: Bicomplex periodic matrices are diagonalizable.

Proof: Let $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ be a Bicomplex periodic matrix of period k

$\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are periodic matrix of period k

$\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are diagonalizable

$\Rightarrow A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is diagonalizable

Proposition 3.6:

Let $A \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a Skew-Periodic matrix with period k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

$$\lambda \in \{0\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 \mid p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \\ \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 + e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

Proof: Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix A associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\Rightarrow AX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow A(AX) = A(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda(AX)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda^2 X$$

$$\Rightarrow A^{k+1} X = \lambda^{k+1} X$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow -AX &= \lambda^{k+1}X && (\because A^{k+1} = -A) \\ \Rightarrow -\lambda X &= \lambda^{k+1}X \\ \Rightarrow (-\lambda - \lambda^{k+1})X &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow (\lambda + \lambda^{k+1})X &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda + {}^1\lambda^{k+1}){}^1X e_1 + ({}^2\lambda + {}^2\lambda^{k+1}){}^2X e_2 &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda + {}^1\lambda^{k+1}){}^1X &= 0 \text{ and } ({}^2\lambda + {}^2\lambda^{k+1}){}^2X = 0 \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda + {}^1\lambda^{k+1} &= 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda + {}^2\lambda^{k+1} = 0 && (\because {}^1X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2X \neq 0) \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda(1 + {}^1\lambda^k) &= 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda(1 + {}^2\lambda^k) = 0 \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 0, (-1)^{\frac{1}{k}} &\text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 0, (-1)^{\frac{1}{k}} \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 0, e^{i_1(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k})}; p = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 &\text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 0, e^{i_1(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k})}; q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \\ \Rightarrow \lambda \in \{0\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k})} e_1 \mid p = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \right\} &\cup \left\{ e^{i_1(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k})} e_2 \mid q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \\ &\cup \left\{ e^{i_1(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k})} e_1 + e^{i_1(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k})} e_2 \mid p, q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Note 3.2: Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a Skew-Periodic matrix with period k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

(i) A contains $(k + 1)^2$ distinct eigenvalues.

(ii) $\|\lambda\| \in \left\{ 0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1 \right\}$

Proposition 3.7: Bicomplex Skew-periodic matrices are diagonalizable.

Proof: Let $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ be a Bicomplex Skew-periodic matrix of period k

$\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are Skew-periodic matrix of period k

$\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are diagonalizable

$\Rightarrow A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is diagonalizable

Proposition 3.8:

Let A is the Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrix of index k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

$$\lambda \in \left\{ e^{i_1(\frac{2p\pi}{k})} e_1 + e^{i_1(\frac{2q\pi}{k})} e_2 \mid p, q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

Proof: Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix A associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\Rightarrow AX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow A(AX) = A(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2X = \lambda(AX)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2X = \lambda(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2X = \lambda^2X$$

$$\Rightarrow A^kX = \lambda^kX$$

$$\Rightarrow IX = \lambda^kX$$

$$(\because A^k = I)$$

$$\Rightarrow X = \lambda^kX$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - \lambda^k)X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - \lambda^k)X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - {}^1\lambda^k){}^1X e_1 + (1 - {}^2\lambda^k){}^2X e_2 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - {}^1\lambda^k){}^1X = 0 \text{ and } (1 - {}^2\lambda^k){}^2X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow 1 - {}^1\lambda^k = 0 \text{ and } 1 - {}^2\lambda^k = 0$$

$$(\because {}^1X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2X \neq 0)$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda^k = 1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda^k = 1$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = (1)^{\frac{1}{k}} \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = (1)^{\frac{1}{k}}$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = e^{i_1(\frac{2p\pi}{k})}; p = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = e^{i_1(\frac{2q\pi}{k})}; q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda \in \left\{ e^{i_1(\frac{2p\pi}{k})} e_1 + e^{i_1(\frac{2q\pi}{k})} e_2 \mid p, q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

Note 3.3: Let A is the Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrix of index k and λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

- (i) A contains k^2 distinct eigenvalues
- (ii) $\|\lambda\| = 1$

Proposition 3.9: Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrices are diagonalizable.

Proof: Let $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ be a Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrix of index k
 $\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are Generalized involutory matrix of index k
 $\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are diagonalizable
 $\Rightarrow A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is diagonalizable

Proposition 3.10:

Let A is the Generalized Bicomplex Skew-involutory matrix of index k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

$$\lambda \in \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 + e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\}.$$

Proof: Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix A associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow AX &= \lambda X \\ \Rightarrow A(AX) &= A(\lambda X) \\ \Rightarrow A^2X &= \lambda(AX) \\ \Rightarrow A^2X &= \lambda(\lambda X) \\ \Rightarrow A^2X &= \lambda^2 X \\ \Rightarrow A^k X &= \lambda^k X \\ \Rightarrow -IX &= \lambda^k X && (\because A^k = -I) \\ \Rightarrow -X &= \lambda^k X \\ \Rightarrow (1 + \lambda^k)X &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow (1 + {}^1\lambda^k)X e_1 + (1 + {}^2\lambda^k)X e_2 &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow (1 + {}^1\lambda^k)X &= 0 \text{ and } (1 + {}^2\lambda^k)X = 0 \\ \Rightarrow 1 + {}^1\lambda^k &= 0 \text{ and } 1 + {}^2\lambda^k = 0 && (\because {}^1X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2X \neq 0) \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda^k &= -1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda^k = -1 \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda &= (-1)^{\frac{1}{k}} \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = (-1)^{\frac{1}{k}} \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda &= e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k} \right)}; p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k} \right)}; q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \\ \Rightarrow \lambda &\in \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 + e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Note 3.4: Let A is the Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrix of index k and λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

- (i) A contains k^2 distinct eigenvalues
- (ii) $\|\lambda\| = 1$

Proposition 3.11: Generalized Bicomplex Skew-involutory matrices are diagonalizable.

Proof: Let $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ be a Bicomplex Skew-involutory matrix of index k
 $\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are Skew-involutory matrix of index k
 $\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are diagonalizable
 $\Rightarrow A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is diagonalizable

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